

EFFECT OF POULTRY MANURE ON NITROGEN AND MOISTURE CONTENT
CONCENTRATION IN THE DRY LEAVES OF *Annona muricata* (linn) SEEDLINGS.

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ABSTRACT

An experiment was conducted to investigate the effect of poultry manure on the nitrogen and moisture content in the dry leaves of *Annona muricata* seedlings at the nursery stage. Pots were randomly arranged using Complete Randomized Designed (CRD). There are tree treatments namely: T1 (which contain 00ppm of poultry manure), T2 (containing 100ppm of poultry manure), T3 (containing 200ppm of poultry manure and T4 (containing 400ppm of poultry manure). Each treatment was replicated four times, making a total of sixteen treatments altogether. Analysis of variance (ANNOVA) and descriptive statistical tools were used to analyse the data obtained. Result of the comparison of the means revealed that the highest concentration of nitrogen and moisture content were recorded with the application of poultry manure at 200ppm (T3). However, treatment (T4) containing 400ppm poultry manure gave the lowest mean reading in all the parameters assessed. Decrease or further increase of poultry manure application from 200ppm reduced percentage of nitrogen and moisture content concentration in the dry leave of *annona muricata* seedlings. The result of the analysis of variance also revealed that there is a significance difference in the mean percentage of moisture content among the different part per million (ppm) of poultry manure used at 5% probability level. However, an insignificant difference was noticed in the nitrogen content. Therefore the use of poultry manure at 200ppm is recommended for foresters and nursery workers for adequate nitrogen and moisture content concentration in the dry leaves of *annona muricata* seedlings at the nursery stage. This will support maximum production of *annona muricata* seedlings, and also enhance the re-use and proper management of poultry manure waste in an economical and environmental friendly manner. Hence, ensuring environmental sustainability with low economic cost.

KEYWORDS: moisture content, environmental sustainability, macronutrient, Organic manure, defoliation Total dry matter,

INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria and other developing countries, addition of organic manure into nursery soil has been the common practice in recent time for the improvement of soil fertility and eventual production of vigorous seedlings. Much research works have been carried out on the use of organic manure in various agricultural and forestry research institutes throughout the country and the result obtained have been positive and satisfactory indeed. However, at the nursery stage, seedlings need adequate moisture and macro nutrient like Nitrogen for rapid development and proper growth. However, little or no research has been carried out to determine the effect of poultry manure on the nitrogen and moisture content of tree seedlings, especially *annona muricata* seedlings at the nursery stage. According to Fagbenro and Adeola (1981), poultry manure has been recognized as effective silvicultural tools for raising healthy forest nursery stock and for hastening growth of trees in the plantation. Hence over the years, the production of quality tree seedlings have become dependent upon the supply of organic material to be used for the improvement of the physical condition of the soil as source of nitrogen and as carrier of fertilizer (Fagbenro 1988). Organic matter like poultry manure reduces loss of water through evaporation. Erosion rate and surface soil temperature are reduced drastically due to presence of organic matter in poultry manure¹. Poultry manure when present in fresh state acts as food source for soil micro organism such as ants, earthworm etc. According to Gunner (2004), organic manure like poultry manure is a major source of Nitrogen, Phosphorous and sulphur. Nitrogen was apparently the first element to be specifically recognized as necessary for plant growth. It is now generally accepted that all life processes depend on nitrogen. Nitrogen is a constituent of purine , pyrimidine and coenzymes which are fundamental units in protein, nucleic acids, the chlorophyll and metabolic enzymes . These together constitutes 40-50 percent of the dry matter in protoplasm. Its function as a vital constituent of chlorophyll and the enzymes thus underlines its central importance in all the metabolic processes in plants (Nwoboshi 2000). It is therefore needed in abundant supply for reproduction,

growth and respiration. Plant that are well supplied with nitrogen have increase leaf size, more photosynthesis and total dry matter. They have dark green leaves and increased size of plant cells. Higher protein content in storage organs and higher water content in fresh plants Which is due to increase protoplasts are also present .(Morton and Watson 1978).Trees need it mainly for wood production and protein synthesis in cell and seeds (Nwoboshi 1982a). Also, the rate of new leaf formation depends on nitrogen supply. In high nitrogen supply conditions, the number of cells of individual leaves increases, while in deficiency conditions , rate of protein synthesis decreases resulting in limited cell division and premature defoliations-another cause of reduced photosynthesis (Cooke 1982)

According to Nwoboshi (1973), deficiency of nitrogen causes a considerable decrease in tree growth. It blocks chlorophyll synthesis, cause some reduction in size and premature senescence of leaves. I may also adversely influence the rate of ribonucleic acids (RNA) protein metabolism in the cytoplasmic structures of the plant cells. Although nitrogen deficient leaves have more stomata per unit area, these tend to react rather sluggishly. The deficiency may also induce xeromorphism, influence viscosity and permeability of cytoplasm as well as impede respiration through lack of substrate caused by depressed photosynthesis.

Annoma muricata, Linn belongs to the family ANNONACEA. It is one of the genus annona that is now widespread in Nigeria (Dulta,1963). It is a small tree of about 8meters in height. The wood is of grey colour and soft. The leaves are simple, alternate, deciduous, and the tree carries dense foliage which seems to attract precipitation of dew in the dry season in Nigeria. It flowers between December and March so that the ripened fruits are available during the raining season between May and September. Hence, it does well in area with an alternation of wet and dry season but prefer a wet season. The perianly is usually in three whorls of three members with each sepal three and petals six in two whorls. The fruits are an aggregate of barrier seeds with the endosperm distinctly ruminated. The fruits are edible and widely cultivated being the most important part of the tree. Its pulp is soft with an aggregate sour flavor usually eaten but may be more acceptable after some preparation as fruit, ice cream and jellies. In West Indies, a fermented drink like “Cidar” is made from it. The fruit contain 110% of sugar mostly glucose and fructose. It is deficient in vitamin A and calcium but rich in vitamin Band C. The unripe fruits are astringent and are used for lack of tone in the intestine and for scruxy in Cote d` ivoire. The unripe fruits are dried and powdered for use against dysentery. The ripe fruits served as bait in fish trap. The flowers are used for cough in Gabon and Cote d` ivoire, in addition both the fruit pod and the flower have been used for catarrh. The seeds contain 45% of a yellow non drying oil which is irritant poison. This is why the seeds are used as fish poison in Madagascar.

Experimental Site

The experiment was carried out at the nursery A of the Federal College of Forestry Ibadan. The College is situated at Jericho quarters in Ibadan North West Local Government Area of Oyo state. It lies between latitude 7° 26 N and longitude 3° 36E. The climate of the area is tropically dominated by rainfall pattern ranges between 1400mm to 1500mm. The average temperature is about 31⁰C to 20⁰C. Relative humidity is about 65%. The eco-climate of the area is rainfall with two distinct seasons which are dry season, (usually commencing from November to March) and rainy season (from April to October) (FRIN, 2011), though there has been some erratic changes within the last decades.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The collected river sand was thoroughly sterilized while the wet poultry manure collected was sun dried for five days, grinded, sieved and measured to different levels (00ppm, 100ppm, 200ppm and 400ppm) into the polythene pots containing 2kg of well sterilized river sand. The poultry manure was grinded, weighed and analyzed in the laboratory. The germinated seedlings were transplanted into pots after two weeks of germination. Initial readings were taken immediately while subsequent one taken fortnightly. After sixteen weeks of thorough observation and measurement, leaves of each treatment were harvested from the parent plant by hand, and were washed with distilled water to kill the likely micro organism present. The wet weight were measured with the aid of beam analytical balance and recorded. Leaves were later enveloped and dried at 60^oc in the oven for 24 hours, after which the dried weight and the moisture content at various level of poultry manure application were determined. The dried leaves of each of the treatments were grinded, digested and distilled before the nitrogen content of the leaves at various levels of treatments were determined titrimetrically.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1, % moisture content in the leaves of *Annona muricata* seedlings at various level of poultry manure application

Treatment	Replicates				TOTAL	MEAN
	R1	R2	R3	R4		
T1 (00ppm)	60	70	76	70	276	69
T2 (100ppm)	132	127	132	132	523	130.8
T3 (200ppm)	132	148	136	124	540	135
T4 (400ppm)	114	114	108	127	463	115.3

Source; Survey(2010).

According to the Table 1, the highest moisture content was obtained from seedlings planted in the media consisting 200ppm of poultry manure (T3), Excess addition of poultry manure (T4- 400ppm) caused decrease in the percentage moisture content of the leaf while any decrease from (T3) 200ppm poultry manure application as seen in (T1)100ppm, T2 (100ppm) respectively will cause decrease in the percentage moisture content present in *Annona muricata* seedlings. This may be link to the result of the poultry manure analysis which reveals that the same gram of poultry manure contain varies percentage of moisture , Nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium.

Table 2: Result of poultry manure Analysis

Mean	%moisture	%N	%P	%K
	75	1.2	0.9	0.8

Source: Laboratory Result (2010).

Table 3: Analysis of variance for moisture content in the leaf of *Annona muricata* Seedlings at various levels of poultry manure application.

SV	DF	SS	MS	FCAL	FTAB	Significance at 5%
Treatment	3	157333	5224443.3	12.7	3.49	S
Error	12	49693.2	4141.1			
Total	15	207026.2				

Source; Survey (2010).

From the Table 2, Ftab (3.49) is less than Fcal (12.7). Hence, there is a significant difference in the mean percentage of moisture content of the four treatments) at p<0.05 level of significance. The significance difference recorded can be linked to the result of the nutritive / chemical analysis of poultry manure which reveals that different part per million of poultry manure contain different percentage of the elements tested (N, P, K and Moisture content). This however supports Bray and Gorham (1964) findings that different organic manure has different proportion of nutrients required for proper plant growth. Nutrient in the poultry manure are transferred to the minerals soil nutrient pool. This result also support Cooke (1982) findings that organic manure and plant have special advantages in growing maximum yield due to their characteristic of improving soil physical properties , supplying nitrogen and all other macro and micro nutrients required for proper plant growth and development.

Table 3 : % Nitrogen concentration in the dry leaves of *Annona muricata* seedlings at Various level of poultry manure application.

Treatments	Replicates				TOTAL	MEAN
	R1	R2	R3	R4		
T1 (00ppm)	2.942	0.525	0.420	0.841	4.728	1.182
T1 (100ppm)	2.102	1.961	2.731	3.047	9.841	2.4603
T3 (200ppm)	1.786	3.152	3.992	1.576	10.506	2.627
T4 (400ppm)	2.207	1.821	2.802	1.891	8.721	2.1803

Source; Survey 2010.

According to Table 3, the highest nitrogen concentration was obtained from the seedlings planted in the media containing 200ppm application of poultry manure (T3). Excess addition of poultry manure caused decrease in the percentage nitrogen content as observed in T4 (400ppm) while any decrease from 200ppm (T3) poultry manure application as noticed in T1(00ppm), and T2 (100ppm) produced lower percentage of nitrogen concentration in the dry leaves of *Annona muricata* seedlings.

Table 4: Analysis of variance for Nitrogen concentration in the dry leaves of *Annona muricata* seedlings at various levels of poultry manure application.

SV	DF	SS	MS	FCAL	FTAB	Significant at 5%
Treatments	3	5.02	1.67	2.23	3.863	NS
Error	9	8.41	0.93			
Total	12	13.43	2.60			0

Source; Survey (2010).

Since Ftab (3.863) is greater than Fcal (2.23), there is no significant difference in the mean percentage of the nitrogen concentration of the four treatments. Moreover, the in significance effect noted with respect to nitrogen concentration at $p < 0.05$ level of significance is an indication that *Annona muricata* seedlings responded negatively to the nitrogen content present poultry manure used.

RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION

The result obtained in this study indicates that *Annona muricata* seedlings respond positively to application of poultry manure in terms of the concentration of nitrogen and moisture content in its dry leaves. Responds to the application of poultry manure appeared to increase with respect to increase in the amount of poultry manure except in T4 (containing 400ppm poultry manure application). The reason for the retardation in the growth parameters observed is considered to be the excess poultry manure applied. However, 200ppm poultry manure appear to be the optimum requirement for the growth of *Annona muricata* seedlings at the nursery provided 2kgrammes of river sand is to be used to fill each of the polythene pots. Therefore, it is recommended that where poultry manure is to be used for raising *Annona muricata* seedlings at nursery stage in a way that will yield high nitrogen and moisture content, then 200ppm of poultry manure application should be used on 2kilogrammes of river sand. Beyond this value, any further application will no more increase but decrease the growth parameters of *Annona muricata* seedlings at the nursery.

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